

Effect of surfactant chain length of cationic micelles of alkyl trimethyl ammonium bromides (C_n TAB) on the spectroscopic properties of 2-anthracene sulphonate[†]

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Abstract : The emission properties of 2-anthracene sulphonate (2-AS) have been studied in cationic micellar media of alkyl trimethyl ammonium bromides (C_n TAB) of varying chain lengths. The effect of chain length of the cationic surfactants on the binding constant values of 2-AS with the micelles has been determined. The location of the probe molecule within the micelles has been ascertained from the emission characteristics of the probe in the presence of the micelles and comparing with that in dioxan-water mixture of varying composition.

Keywords : Fluorescence, polarity, exciplex, binding constant, chain length.

Introduction

The importance of micelles, which are used as membrane biomimetic agents in biological systems, lies in their capacity to provide a matrix for arranging the reaction sequentially for efficient interaction, i.e. they help in compartmentalization of the reactants dynamically¹⁻¹⁰. Surfactant entrapped water molecules provide unique microenvironments for interactions and reactions, as a result of which attention has been drawn to the effect of micelles on the nature and rates of reactions. Water molecules, which are tightly bound to the surfactant head groups of micelles, resemble the hydrophilic pockets of enzymes and have high viscosities, low mobilities and polarities^{11,12}. Anthracene is a highly fluorescent molecule. Anthracene and its derivatives are used as fluorescent probes for the study of dynamics of biological molecules. Furthermore because of their good quantum yield efficiency for triplet state generation, they have provided some information on triplet state photophysics of organic molecules leading to better knowledge of their structure and reactivity. On sulphonation, the monosulphonate formed becomes water soluble and produces interesting fluorescent characteristics. The sulphonate group affects the overall symmetry of the anthracene moiety and also

introduces negatively charged centers in the molecule. Since anthracene sulphonates are amphiphilic in nature, two types of water matrix around the 2-AS molecules are considered (1) a hydrogen bonded structure around the hydrophilic SO_3^- groups and (2) an ice like water structure around the hydrophobic region of the anthracene skeleton. The hydrophobic water clusters are more tightly bound internally than the hydrogen bonded water structure around the hydrophilic region. The hydrophobic hydration in the excited state has an important bearing on the study of biological molecules such as proteins, nucleic acids and their aggregates. The photophysics and photochemistry of anthracene sulphonates have been studied earlier¹³⁻¹⁶. It has been found that the reactivity of the micelles of C_n TAB series depends on the length of non-polar tail of the surfactants^{17,18}. As an extension of the study, the role of chain lengths of cationic surfactants of a homologous series on the photophysics of 2-AS has been investigated. Such investigation using this probe is rare in literature. The choice of fluorescent probe molecule is of course important because its residence depth in the interface of micelles is used to estimate the polarity and nature of the region in which it is located. In this report, the fluorescence characteristics of 2-AS in micel-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

lar solutions of CTAB, TTAB and DTAB were studied to investigate the role of hydrophobic chain length of the cationic surfactants of a homologous series, on the photophysics of 2-AS.

Experimental

2-Anthracene sulphonate was prepared by reducing the corresponding anthraquinone with Zn dust and 20% NaOH solution for 4–6 h. The products were treated with active charcoal to remove traces of anthraquinone and other impurities, crystallized four times from water and obtained as sodium salt. CTAB, TTAB, DTAB were of Aldrich products. The characterization and purity of the compounds were checked by emission measurement and impurities were found to be absent. The emission spectrum of 2-AS was recorded in the range 370–500 nm by exciting 2-AS molecules at 359 nm in a fluorescence spectrophotometer (Fluorolog FIII A Spectrofluorimeter, Spex Inc, NJ, USA) with a slit width of 1.25 mm. The concentration of 2-AS used in micellar solutions was of the order of 10^{-3} mmol dm $^{-3}$. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Pharmaspec UV-Vis 1700 spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, with a matched pair of silica cuvettes (path length 1 cm). Absorbance and emission spectra of the probe in varying composition of dioxan-water mixture were also recorded to determine the polarity of the microenvironment surrounding the probe molecules. The effect of urea on probe surrounding micellar environment has also been studied.

Results and discussion

Absorbance and fluorescence :

2-AS has absorbance maxima at 359 nm and emission maxima at 415 nm. In presence of the cationic micelles, there is no change in the wavelength of absorption maxima and absorbance. This indicates that there is no interaction of 2-AS with the micelles in the ground state. Before cmc, the fluorescence intensity of 2-AS decreases in the surfactant solutions. After the cmc, the fluorescence intensity is enhanced with vibrational features and becomes maximum at higher micellar concentration. The decrease in fluorescence intensity upon addition of cationic surfactants in the pre-micellar range may be due to the formation of an association complex or exciplex, between the excited anionic probe and cationic surfactants due to electrostatic attraction. Similar cases have also been observed with anionic probe pyranine and CTAB¹⁹. The changes observed in the fluorescence spectra of 2-AS as a func-

tion of C_nTAB concentration is presented in Fig. 1. Fluorescence intensity was plotted as a function of concentration of the surfactants (Fig. 2). From the break of the two curves the cmc values of the surfactants have been determined and are presented in Table 1. The values are close

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectra of 2-AS in CTAB, [2-AS] = 6.4×10^{-6} M.

Fig. 2. Plot of fluorescence intensities of 2-AS vs $-\log$ of surfactant concentration, [2-AS] = 6.4×10^{-6} M.

Surfactant	Binding constants (K) $\times 10^{-4}$ (dm 3 mol $^{-1}$)	cmc (from F.I. plot) (mmol dm $^{-3}$)	cmc ^d (from literature) (mmol dm $^{-3}$)	E _T (30) (kcal mol $^{-1}$)
CTAB	4.94	0.8	0.8	56.17
TTAB	1.94	3.1	3.5	58.76
DTAB	1.22	13.5	15	60.55

^dRef. 20.

to the literature values²⁰. These spectral data were used to calculate the binding constant K , in the excited state for the substrate micelle interaction. The interface of the cationic micelles being positively charged helps the anionic 2-AS molecules orient towards the interface by electrostatic attraction.

Determination of probe-micelle binding constants :

The micelles may be considered as individual compartment and multiple equilibria model^{21,22} may be considered for micellization of the solute. For a given concentration of the solutes and the micelle, the solute will be distributed between the aqueous phase (S_w) and the micellar phase (S_m) according to the model

$$S_w + M = S_m \quad (1)$$

The binding constant (K) for solute-micelle interaction is

$$K = [S_m] / ([S_w][M]) \text{ or, } K[M] = [S_m] / [S_w]$$

where $[S_m]$ and $[S_w]$ represent the concentration of the solutes in the micellar phase and the aqueous phase respectively, $[M]$ is the effective micellar concentration. For a given value of $[M]$, $K[M]$ assumes the role of partition coefficient for the solute in two phases. Assuming that the observed fluorescence intensity (F) in the solution is the sum of the fractional fluorescence intensities in the aqueous phase (F_w) and in the micellar phase (F_m), the expression (2) can be deduced considering equilibrium (1).

The binding constant K of 2-AS with the micelles has been determined using the relation²³ given below.

$$(F_w - F)^{-1} = (F_w - F_m)^{-1} [1 + (K[M])^{-1}] \quad (2)$$

where, F , F_w and F_m represent the fluorescence intensities of 2-AS in micellar solution, water and micellar solution showing maximum fluorescence intensity respectively. $[M]$ is the effective micellar concentration.

$$M = ([\text{Surfactant}] - \text{cmc})/n,$$

where, n is the aggregation number. K values were determined from the slope of the plot of $(F_w - F_m)(F_w - F)^{-1}$ vs $1/[M]$ and the values are given in Table 1. The binding constant values increase with increase in chain length of the alkyl segments of the surfactants. In other words, the probe is fairly bound with the micelles in the order CTAB > TTAB > DTAB.

Location of probe molecules in the micellar phase :

The location of the probe molecules in the micellar phase has been determined by comparing the observed

spectral changes of 2-AS in micellar media with the spectral changes of the probe in varying composition of dioxan-water. The fluorescence spectra of 2-AS in dioxan-water mixture (Fig. 3) are alike the spectra of 2-AS in the micellar media (Fig. 1). It is evident that the ratio of the peak heights of 1-0 and 0-0 vibrational bands of 2-AS vary in different environments like the variation in intensity of different peaks of pyrene in different solvents²⁴. The peak height ratio (F_1/F_2) of 2-AS in different dioxan-water composition has been plotted against the E_T (30) values of the medium (Fig. 4). A linear curve is obtained. The shift in wavelength maxima of 2-AS was also plotted against the E_T (30) values of varying dioxan-

Fig. 3. Fluorescence spectra of 2-AS in water-dioxan mixture. Dioxan (v/v) : (1) 0%, (2) 10%, (3) 20%, (4) 30%, (5) 40%, (6) 50%, (7) 60%, (8) 70%, (9) 80%, (10) 90%, (11) 100%, $[2\text{-AS}] = 6.4 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Fig. 4. Plot of F_1/F_2 of 2-AS vs E_T (30) of dioxan-water mixture, $[2\text{-AS}] = 6.4 \times 10^{-6} M$.

Fig. 5. Plot of shift in wavelength maxima of 2-AS vs $E_T(30)$ of dioxan-water mixture, $[2\text{-AS}] = 6.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$.

water composition (Fig. 5). Assuming that the same relation is also obeyed in the micellar medium and comparing the peak height ratio in the micellar media, the $E_T(30)$ value of the micellar region surrounding the probe has been determined and the values are given in Table 1. From this observation one can infer that 2-AS is located at the interfacial region and its motion is restricted. The most likely situation is that the negatively charged sulphonate molecules reside near the positively charged surface of the hydrophilic region of the micelles and the hydrocarbon ring towards the hydrophobic region of the micelles. Before cmc, the initial decrease in fluorescence intensity may be due to the electrostatic attraction of the negatively charged probe molecules with the positively charged surfactant monomers and the resultant species formed has low fluorescence intensity than the probe itself. The gradual increase in fluorescence intensity after cmc, is the intensity of the probe molecules in the completely micellized states. When urea (1 mM to 8 mM) was added in the micellar solutions of 2-AS, the nature of the fluorescence spectra of 2-AS did not change and the fluorescence intensities were almost identical. This indicates that urea was unable to loosen the strong electrostatic binding between the negatively charged probe and the positively charged micellar surface. The strong binding between the probe and the micelles is also evident from the high binding constant values of 2-AS in different micellar media (Table 1). A plot of $\log K$ values against the number of carbon atoms in the hydrophobic chain of the surfactants (Fig. 6) shows that with increase

Fig. 6. Plot of $\log K$ vs number of carbon atoms in the hydrophobic chain of the surfactants.

in the surfactant chain length, the binding of the probe with the micelles becomes stronger.

Conclusion :

The present work deals with the excited state sensitivity of 2-anthracene sulphonate (2-AS) in micellar media, although the ground state absorption remains unperturbed. Fluorescence intensity of 2-anthracene sulphonate, a negatively charged probe, is quenched by cationic surfactant solution of alkyl trimethyl ammonium bromides but the fluorescence intensity is enhanced in the micellar solution of the same surfactants after their cmc and the spectra is very similar to that of 2-AS in varying composition of dioxan-water mixture. This clearly indicates about the fluorescence sensitivity of the probe towards the polarity of the microheterogeneous environment surrounding the probe. The location of the probe molecules within the micelles has been ascertained from the emission characteristics of the probe in the presence of the micelles and comparing with that in dioxan-water mixture of varying composition and it was observed that the probe molecules reside at the micellar interface. From the binding constant values, it is concluded that the binding of 2-AS with the micelles depend on the alkyl chain length of the surfactants. The binding constant values are in the order $\text{CTAB} > \text{TTAB} > \text{DTAB}$, which shows that an increase in alkyl chain length of the surfactants leads to a stronger binding between the probe and the micelles. Fluorescence spectral studies of 2-AS in micellar medium have established that 2-AS can be used as a probe for water pools in membranes and micelles. This work will also help to

choose the surfactant of proper alkyl chain length for forming a micelle, which can be used as a micro reactor for drug delivery in biological systems.

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